

Divergence between awareness and uptake of cervical cancer screening among female hospital workers: a single-centre experience in Northeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Nigeria bears a significant burden of cervical cancer. Yet, personal screening uptake even among hospital workers is suspected to be low. This study investigated attitudes, determinants and deterrents of cervical screening among female tertiary hospital workers in a northeastern Nigerian community and suggested interventions to remedy them. **Materials and Methods:** A *de novo* semi-structured questionnaire containing 49 data items categorised into four domains - sociodemographic, awareness about cervical cancer, reproductive, and social characteristics - was distributed among female staff of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise proportions with appropriate 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) and chi-square tests were used to assess associations. **Results:** The majority (85.6%) of the 160 participants enrolled in this study had at least a secondary level of education. Whereas participants-reported awareness of cervical cancer stood at 70% (112 participants) with 95% CI of 0.36-0.51, only 41.3% (95% CI 0.19-0.33) of the total sample (67 out of 160) could name a screening method, while more than 95% had never been screened previously. Risk factors identified by participants were early age at sexual debut and marriage (25%), multiparity (36.2%), multiple sexual partners (16.3%), unprotected sexual intercourse (75.6%), use of contraceptives (35.7%), and history of sexually transmitted infections (10.6%). Receiver-initiated screening was associated with being aware of screening availability ($p=0.016$), previous 3 or more pregnancies ($p=0.030$) and monthly income level exceeding N50,000/\$34.00 ($p=0.042$). Lack of awareness of service points (20%) and lack of interest/poor risk perception (40%) were common reasons for not seeking screening. Furthermore, about a third of the participants (34.4%) indicated a willingness to screen if it were made available. **Conclusion:** This study found a remarkable low screening uptake among the participants. Identified factors of failure to engage with screening services should be comprehensively addressed.

Keywords: Awareness knowledge and attitude, Cervical cancer screening, Female Hospital Workers, Northeastern Nigeria.

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20667938>

Date Submitted: 27th March 2026

Date Accepted: 2nd May 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as: Uchenna S. Ezenkwa, Dauda A. Katagum, Sunday E. Achanya, Hassan T. Olayinka, Zakia Muhammad, Amina O. Muhammed, Abubakar H. Nuhu, Mairo U. Kadaura, Musa A. Garbati, Ado D. Geidam, Babagana Bako, Matthew Schlumbrecht, Sophia H. L. George, Bala M. Audu. Divergence between awareness and uptake of cervical cancer screening among female hospital workers: a single-centre experience in Northeastern Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Sci* 2026; 2(1): 134-143

Introduction

Cervical cancer, a malignancy affecting the lowest part of the uterus (cervix), is a disease of public health importance. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) in its recent report, it is the fourth most common cancer among women worldwide, with approximately 660,000 new cases and a leading cause of cancer-related deaths in 37 countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, South America and Southeast Asia.¹ Notably, cervical cancer develops through a long premalignant phase, making it preventable through screening.² However, the absence of national control programs including vaccination against high-risk Human Papillomavirus (hr-HPV) infection and early detection screening, contributes significantly to the high incidence rates of this disease in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC).³

In Nigeria, the burden of cervical cancer is substantial, with about 12,075 new cases and 7,968 deaths annually. This figure is projected to increase to 19,440 new cases and 10,991 deaths by 2025.^{4,5} Despite this, only about 9% of eligible women have undergone screening for cervical cancer in the country, highlighting the urgent need for improved prevention and control measures.⁶

In Northern Nigeria, cervical cancer constitutes a significant health problem, accounting for 19.6% to 65.7% of gynaecological cancers in the northeastern and northwestern regions.⁷⁻⁹ The high burden of the disease in this area is attributed to several factors, including persistent infection of the cervix by high-risk Human Papillomavirus (hr-HPV), which is a necessary factor in cervical cancer development. Studies have shown that nearly half (48%) of women undergoing cervical screening in northeastern Nigeria have detectable hr-HPV.¹⁰ Additionally, other risk factors prevalent in this population include early age at first sexual intercourse, multiple sexual partners, multiparity, and early age at marriage.¹⁰

Limited knowledge and awareness about cervical cancer and its risk factors have been identified as major contributors to the poor uptake of cervical cancer screening in Nigeria, in addition to the absence of a national preventive policy.^{5,6,11} This is particularly striking in northern Nigeria, where awareness levels are extremely low.^{8,10,12} In contrast, female hospital workers (FHWs) in Nigeria have demonstrated adequate knowledge about cervical cancer.¹³ However, it is unclear whether this knowledge translates to actual screening uptake among FHWs in this region, highlighting the need for this study.

Hospital workers, especially FHWs, serve as role models in their communities, making their utilisation of cervical screening services a significant indicator of the general population's behaviour. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the relationship between FHWs' awareness, knowledge and attitudes towards cervical screening and their uptake of the service. This study aims to determine if awareness positively influences screening utilisation among FHWs in northeastern Nigeria and identify factors that inhibit screening uptake. Furthermore, by exploring the status of FHWs' awareness and screening behaviour, we can develop effective strategies to scale up screening rates and ultimately reduce the burden of cervical cancer in northeastern Nigeria in particular. In addition, the findings of this study can inform policy changes in the design of targeted national interventions to eliminate cervical cancer in Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Study design and Location

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study using a self-administered *de novo* questionnaire conducted among consenting female hospital workers of Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare (FUHSTHA) located in the Northern part of Bauchi state, Northeastern Nigeria (supplementary Figure 1). The hospital has been in existence for about 20 years and offers cervical cancer screening services daily, accessible to both hospital staff and the public.

Supplementary Fig. 1: Approximate location of Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare Teaching Hospital, Bauchi state, Nigeria

#Study participants and Sample size determination

This study was conducted between August and December 2023. There were 356 female staff working at the FUHSTH Azare at the time of this study, and they were considered eligible to participate. These were employed in the various sections of the hospital workforce, both in the administrative and clinical arms. Using the Taro Yamane formula.¹⁴ A sample size of 188 participants was determined as adequate for the population. To this was added a non-response rate of 10% (18 participants), giving an anticipated total of 206 participants for enrolment into the study.

Study instrument and data collection

A semi-structured questionnaire comprising four domains was used to collect data from consenting participants. The first domain covered socio-demographics, including age, highest level of education achieved, marital status, religion, and monthly income. The second domain focused on cervical cancer awareness and included questions to determine if participants had ever heard of cervical cancer, HPV, vaccination against HPV, knowledge about screening methods, and prior screening. The third and fourth domains addressed personal risk factors among the participants and were classified as reproductive and social, respectively. The developed instrument was

pretested among female hospital workers (FHWs) at a General Hospital in the community to assess its reliability and yielded a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.75 (data not published).

A convenience sampling method was used to recruit 206 female staff members of FUHSTHA who gave consent to participate in the study. The questionnaire was distributed to participants over a two-week period and was self-administered, with participants' privacy and anonymity maintained throughout the study.

Data analysis

The obtained data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Non-numerical data were presented as frequencies and percentages with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI), while the continuous variable (age) was presented as the median and interquartile range. Chi-square, Fisher Exact tests and likelihood ratio tests, where appropriate, were used to examine associations between screening uptake and demographic variables, with $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed) indicating statistical significance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the institution's Ethics, Research, and Review Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants enrolled in this study, ensuring the utmost confidentiality of participants' data throughout all stages of this work. Institutional and Helsinki guidelines on the protection of human subjects participating in research were followed diligently.

Results

One hundred and sixty out of 206 questionnaires were returned, resulting in a 77.7% response rate.

The majority of the respondents (44.2%) were between 20 and 29 years old, with a median age of 30 years and an interquartile range of 13 years.

Table 1 contains additional sociodemographic characteristics of the study participants, including educational attainment, marital status, religious affiliation, occupation, and average monthly income. The majority of respondents (over 80%) had secondary education or higher, while about 3% had no formal education. Most respondents were married (58.8%) and identified as Muslims (70%). Although all respondents worked in the hospital, their occupations varied, with the majority identifying as civil servants (73.1%). Nearly half earned below the median monthly income of fifty

thousand naira (~\$34 USD), and about 67.5% had children.

Table 1 presents the respondents' socioeconomic demographic data

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percent age (%)
Age group (in decades)	10-19	1	0.6
	20-29	68	44.2
	30-39	55	35.7
	40-49	24	15.6
	50-59	6	3.9
Educational status	Primary	11	6.9
	Secondary	35	21.9
	Tertiary	102	63.7
	None	5	3.1
	No response	7	4.4
Marital status	Single	42	26.3
	Married	94	58.8
	Separated/divorced	10	6.2
	Widowed	6	3.7
	No response	8	5.0
Religion	Christianity	43	26.8
	Islam	112	70
	Others	2	1.3
	No response	3	1.9
	Civil servant	117	73.1
Occupation	Nurse/Midwife	17	10.6
	Medical	6	3.8
	Doctor	17	10.6
	MLS		
	Missing		
Monthly Income ₦	≤ 50,000 (\$34)	72	45
	> 50,000 (\$34)	51	31.9
	No response	37	23.1

MLS: Medical laboratory scientist

Table 2 describes participants' awareness of cervical cancer, uptake of cervical cancer screening. The findings revealed that 70% had heard of cervical cancer (n=112), and 39.3% (n = 63) identified HPV as the cause of cervical cancer. Among those who knew about screening (n = 73), 66 (90.4%) mentioned Pap smear, visual inspection with acetic acid or Lugol's iodine, and HPV testing as screening modalities, resulting in 41.3% (95% CI 0.19-0.33) of participants (66 out of 160) with a functional knowledge of screening modalities.

Table 3 presents the attitude towards cervical cancer screening. As shown, only 7 (4.4%) participants (95% CI 0.01-0.06) had a personal history of screening, with 6 having used pap tests. Among those who had never been screened, 20% (n = 42) reported a lack of opportunity or knowledge of where to obtain screening services, 40% (n = 71) had no interest or perceived themselves as low risk, and 3 respondents did not

Table 2: Cervical Cancer Awareness

Data item	Category	Frequency (%)
Have you heard of cervical cancer before?	Yes	112 (70)
	No	45 (28.1)
What causes cervical cancer?	No response	3 (1.9)
	Early Menarche/vaginal insert	2 (1.3)
	HPV	63 (39.3)
	Infection	23 (14.4)
	Many sexual partners	2 (1.3)
Have you heard of cervical screening?	No response	63 (39.3)
	Unknown	7 (4.4)
	No response	1 (0.6)
Are you aware of any screening method?	Yes	89 (55.6)
	No	70 (43.8)
Have you heard of Human Papilloma virus?	No response	1 (0.6)
	Yes	73 (45.6)
Have you heard of Human Papilloma virus?	No	83 (51.9)
	No response	4 (2.5)
Have you heard of Human Papilloma virus?	Yes	102 (63.7)
	No	54 (33.8)
Have you heard of Human Papilloma virus?	No response	4 (2.5)

see any need to screen since they had not been sexually exposed. Furthermore, while 34.4% indicated willingness to undergo screening if available, 8.8% responded "No", and 56.8% did not provide an answer. This high non-response rate represents a silent majority whose perspectives are unarticulated but critically important for programme design.

Table 4 presents information on the social demographics of the population, including type of marriage, smoking habits, condom use, alcohol consumption, contraceptive use, history of STIs, and family history of cervical cancer. Most respondents were in monogamous marriages (61.2%), had never smoked cigarettes (94.4%), and had never consumed alcoholic beverages (90.6%).

Table 3 Attitude to Cervical Screening

Data item	Category	Frequency (%)
Have you ever been screened for cervical cancer?	Yes	7 (4.4)
	No	151 (94.3)
	No response	2 (1.3)
Have you received HPV vaccine?	Yes	10 (6.3)
	No	146 (91.2)
	No response	4 (2.5)
Would you be willing to undergo screening if it were made available?	Yes	55 (34.4)
	No	14 (8.8)
	No response	91 (56.8)

The use of condoms for protection against sexually transmitted infections (STIs) was practised occasionally by 19.4% of the respondents, while about 75.4% said they had never used them (75.4%),

and 5% did not respond to the question. Regarding oral contraceptive use and cervical cancer, over one-third (35%) of the participants reported using birth control pills to regulate births. Additionally, about one in ten people reported ever having had an STI, while 6.25% of participants reported a positive family history of cervical cancer.

Table 5 examines the association between different variables and the uptake of cervical cancer screening. Factors significantly associated with screening uptake included awareness of cervical cancer screening ($p = 0.016$), a higher number of pregnancies ($p = 0.030$) and a higher income level ($p = 0.042$). Marital status, religious affiliation, awareness of cervical cancer, and family history of cancer had no significant association with the uptake of screening services.

Discussion

This study revealed a disturbingly low rate of cervical cancer screening uptake among FHWs in a tertiary hospital in northeastern Nigeria, despite their high level of awareness of the disease, reflecting a state of strong discomfort to screening. This finding is consistent with previous studies in northeastern Nigeria (Ilorin and Maiduguri) but differs from the higher screening rates reported among FHW in the southern part of the country.^{12,15-18} Factors such as lack of awareness, multiparity, and low socio-economic status have been identified as barriers to screening in other studies in Nigeria and neighbouring sub-Saharan African countries.¹⁸⁻²³ These findings suggest suggest that these factors may interact in unique ways to deter eligible, knowledgeable women from accessing services, potentially due to sociocultural norms specific to this population.

One of the major issues identified in the current investigation was the lack of awareness about screening services and where to obtain them. This underscores the necessity for advocacy to improve access to screening. However, lack of awareness cannot explain the significant gap between those who did not screen but were aware of the screening services. Other factors could account for this observation. For example, about a fifth of respondents reported being unable to screen because they did not know where the services were offered. Other authors have also shown similar reasons as deterrents for screening.²⁴ Thus, advocacy about the disease should explore various

aspects of knowledge that would benefit the target audience, including information not just about screening, but also where such services can be obtained. This study also found that a low perceived risk of cervical cancer may be a significant contributor to the low uptake of screening services.

Table 4 displays respondents’ Reproductive and Socio-behavioural Characteristics, indicating Cervical cancer risk

Data item	Category	Frequency (%)
Type of marriage	Monogamous	98 (61.2)
	Polygamous	26 (16.3)
	No response	36 (22.5)
Number of pregnancies	0-2	83 (51.9)
	3-5	46 (28.8)
	≥ 6	19 (11.8)
	No response	12 (7.5)
Number of children	0-2	91 (56.9)
	3-5	41 (25.6)
	≥ 6	16 (10.6)
	No response	12 (7.5)
Do you smoke cigarettes?	Never	151 (94.4)
	Yes	5 (3.1)
	No response	4 (2.4)
Do you use condom?	Yes/Occasionally	31 (19.4)
	Never	121 (75.6)
	No response	8 (5.0)
Do you use birth control pills?	Yes	57 (35.7)
	Never	98 (61.2)
	No response	5 (3.1)
Do you drink alcohol?	Yes	10 (6.3)
	Never	145 (90.6)
	No response	5 (3.1)
Are you on long-term steroid therapy?	Yes	4 (2.5)
	No	150 (93.7)
	No response	6 (0.6)
Have you ever had any STI before?	Yes	17 (10.6)
	No	128 (80.0)
	No response	15 (9.4)
Have you ever had abnormal vaginal discharge?	Yes	25 (15.6)
	No	132 (82.5)
	No response	3 (1.9)
Have you had abnormal vaginal bleeding?	Yes	2 (1.2)
	No	155 (96.9)
	No response	3 (1.9)
Do you have bleeding after sex?	Yes	8 (5.0)
	No	144 (90.0)
	No response	8 (5.0)
Do you know anyone in your family who has ever had cervical cancer?	Yes	10 (6.2)
	No	147 (91.9)
	No response	3 (1.9)

Table 5 Association between screening uptake and sociodemographic variables

Variable	Category	Ever screened for cervical cancer		Total (valid n)	P-value
		Yes	No		
Heard of cervical cancer	No	0	43	154	0.192
	Yes	7	104		
Marital status	Divorced	0	10	150	0.429
	Married	6	86		
	Single	0	42		
	Widowed	0	6		
Heard of cervical screening	No	0	70	159	0.016*
	Yes	7	82		
Family History of cervical cancer	No	6	140	156	0.377
	Yes	1	9		
Number of pregnancies	0-2	1	82	148	0.030*
	3-5	5	41		
	≥ 6	0	19		
Average monthly income (₦)	< 50,000 (\$34)	1	71	122	0.042*
	> 50,000 (\$34)	5	45		
Religion	Christianity	4	39	155	0.178
	Islam	3	107		
	Others	0	2		
Occupation	Civil servant	4	113	143	0.229
	Health workers	2	24		

*Significant level < 0.05

Analysis was restricted to respondents with complete data (valid n). Non-response entries were excluded.

Despite being exposed to known risk factors, many respondents believed they were not at risk of developing cervical cancer. This is consistent with a review of Nigerian studies, which showed that most participants in 10 out of 15 articles believed screening was unnecessary due to a lack of knowledge of symptoms, belief that cervical cancer is incurable, or simply a lack of interest in screening.²⁵ This highlights that awareness alone is insufficient; it needs to be complemented with education about the causal link between the virus and cancer, including the progression from infection to latency and eventually, disease. This comprehensive approach will enable women to accurately assess their risk status, weigh risk factors appropriately, and encourage early screening among those at risk.²⁶

Low income and socioeconomic status were also significant barriers to cervical cancer screening in this study. Research in Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria, showed that individuals with lower socioeconomic status were less likely to seek healthcare even when they were ill.²⁷ Specifically, households earning less than 30,000 Naira per month (\$34 USD) were less likely to utilise healthcare services.²⁸ Cervical cancer

screening is particularly challenging because eligible women are often healthy and may not see the need for preventive care, which can be costly. Studies in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa consistently show that cost is a major deterrent to screening.^{25,29} The WHO advocates for low-cost screening methods and country-led policies and action plans, communicated at all levels of care and in the community.³⁰

A high non-response rate on several questions related to sexual behaviour (e.g., 22.5% for type of marriage) and attitude towards cervical screening (58.8% for willingness to screen) was observed in this study, suggesting that the participants may have found the questions intrusive or uncomfortable. These could be rooted in sociocultural contexts where sexual health issues are likely stigmatised.³¹ One such cultural influence among the populace is the belief that cancer is caused by evil spirits or witches and should therefore not be treated in the hospital.³² Such beliefs are usually deeply ingrained, making individuals averse to screening and even viewing screening recommendations as ill-advised. Other socioeconomic factors include the likely influence of men's traditional role women's healthcare seeking decisions.³³ In addition, cultural beliefs and misconceptions can promote medical mistrust, arising from misinformation around health

services, leading to suspicion of the healthcare system and providers.³⁵ Such mistrust could result in failure to volunteer private information observed in this study. Addressing this will require culturally sensitive, locally adaptable strategies.³⁴ Studies in sub-Saharan Africa have shown that involving the community in health education and decision-making potentially increases knowledge and prevention of cervical cancer.^{36,37} Involving community members in all the phases of service delivery can help align interventions with local needs and values, leading to greater impact.^{36,38} Such partnerships are fundamental, especially in disadvantaged contexts.³⁹

Whereas Nigeria has an existing National Cancer Control Plan that prioritises cervical cancer control, its impact on increasing screening is potentially contingent on advocacy for its provisions.^{40,41} It has been shown that countries with organised nationwide programs or health insurance practices experience significantly better screening rates.⁴² Given the cultural contexts potentially at play in the present study, region-specific, actionable prevention strategies are warranted, such as female-only screening days, integrating screening with antenatal services, and involving community health educators to increase programme buy-in and thereby scale up screening uptake.

Limitations of the study

There were limitations to this study. Firstly, the observed attrition rate of 15% was higher than expected. Secondly, some participants did not fully respond to questions exploring attitudes, which may have affected the validity of the observations. The self-administration of questionnaires, while necessary given the study setting, may have contributed to this limitation. Thirdly, the use of a convenience sampling approach may have introduced bias, as not all eligible participants had an equal chance of being included in the study. The small study population and the shift-work nature of some categories of workers further limited participation. Furthermore, given the small number of screened participants, multivariate analysis to exclude confounders of service uptake was not conducted as it precludes definitive conclusions on predictors of uptake. Lastly, the study did not explore the potential role of sociocultural contexts, such as husbands' and parents' influence on women's access to cervical screening. Future studies should address these limitations to

determine if the findings differ from those of this study.

Conclusion

Female hospital workers in this study showed remarkably low cervical screening uptake despite their moderate level of awareness about the disease. Identified deterrents, including low economic status, self-reported low risk perception, and inadequate communication of service availability, deserve dedicated efforts to resolve. Future studies focused on culture context-specific frameworks that could explain the observed discomforts around sexual health conversations should also be designed to interrogate this outcome more closely. Findings from such studies are needed to support policymaking.

Funding

This work was supported by the tertiary education trust fund grant TETF/DR&D/CE/UNI/AZARE/IBR/2023/VOL 1

Conflict of interest

- The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.
- The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.
- All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.
- The authors have no financial or proprietary interests in any material discussed in this article.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by [BMA] [USE], [SEA], [ZM], [AOM] and [AHN]. The first draft of the manuscript was written by [USE], and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript

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